

Synergistic effects of neutral donors on the extraction of uranium(VI) by *N*-acetyl benzamide in chloroform

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Abstract : The extraction behaviour of U^{VI} from an aqueous nitrate medium employing *N*-acetyl benzamide in chloroform has been investigated in presence of several donors like trioctyl phosphine oxide, pyridine and dimethyl sulphoxide. The metal was assayed by UV-Vis spectrophotometry method. The overall equilibrium constant for each of the three ternary extraction systems were estimated and role of different thermodynamic parameters are discussed.

Keywords : Uranium extraction, UV-Vis spectroscopy, *N*-acetyl benzamide.

Introduction

Uranium as a nuclear fuel, occupies strategically important focus of any nuclear program. Therefore, the extractive separation of uranium(VI) and its chemical characterization for impurities at trace and ultratrace levels, before being used as fuel in nuclear reactors, has been widely emphasised^{1,2}. The recovery of uranium from rare earth elements has been the focus of various researchers not only due to its association with rare earth elements in nature but also for reprocessing of nuclear fuel³. Uranium is an actinide element of a special importance in nuclear technology due to the fission property of ^{235}U and the presence of the fertile ^{238}U in natural uranium up to may the percentage 99.3%. Uranium exist in aqueous solution as U^{III} , U^{IV} , U^V and U^{VI} among which the tetravalent and hexavalent uranium are generally very stable⁴. Separation and purification of U^{VI} from nitric acid medium has been generally carried out by organophosphorous extractants like TBP, trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO), and di(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid (DEHPA)⁵⁻⁷. Therefore, the present work reports the extraction of uranium(VI) with binary mixtures of the *N*-benzoyl acetamide and various neutral donors such as like trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO), pyridine and dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO). Major advantages of the synergistic extraction include low ligand inventory and possibility of extraction from high concentration of acids or complexing agents Sev-

eral synergistic extraction studies of metal ions are reported with neutral oxodonsors from different acid media⁸⁻¹¹. However combination of acid amide with organophosphorus donors for extraction of U^{VI} has not been previously reported. In the present investigation, such organophosphorus donors have been compared with two different classes of bases in relation to synergistic effect on uranium(VI) extraction. An attempt to elucidate the extraction mechanism has also been offered.

Results and discussion

Effect of equilibration time :

The extraction of U^{VI} by *N*-benzoyl acetamide (HL) in chloroform show that the two phase reaction is fairly rapid and the equilibrium is reached within 30 min. The increase of the time of equilibration does not affect the extraction equilibrium.

Effect of equilibrium pH :

It is known that the acidity of the aqueous solution strongly affects the efficiency of the uranium(VI) extraction by acidic extractants like β -diketone reagents. Extraction of uranium(VI) as a function of pH in chloroform has been studied over the pH range of 1.0-4.0. The extraction was quantitative in the pH range 2.0-3.0. The plot of $\log D_0$ vs pH (in the pH range 2.0-3.0) yields a straight line with a slope ~ 2 (Fig. 1) indicating that only two H^+ ions were liberated from the ligand on complex-

Fig. 1. Variation of uranium(VI) distribution ratios with pH-values at fixed concentration of $2.106 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ *N*-acetyl benzamide in chloroform.

ation with uranium(VI) producing extractable species in the organic phase. An optimum pH of 3.0 was selected for the further experiments [D_o = distribution co-efficient in presence of only extractant].

Effect of diluents :

It is well known that in all solvent extraction systems, the diluent plays an important role¹². Few organic solvents of different dielectric constants like carbontetrachloride (CCl_4), chloroform (CHCl_3), xylene, toluene, methyl isobutyl ketone, *n*-butanol, and nitrobenzene were chosen to study the effects of diluents on the extraction of uranium(VI) from aqueous nitrate solution at equilibrium pH 3.0. From the D_o values (Table 1), it is seen that the extraction of the uranium(VI) with a fixed concentration of ($2.106 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) *N*-benzoyl acetamide was maximum in the case of chloroform and minimum for *n*-

Table 1. Extraction of U^{VI} with *N*-acetyl benzamide in different solvents from aqueous nitrate medium at pH 3.0

Solvent	Dielectric constant (ϵ)	Distribution coefficient (D_o)
Chloroform	4.62	5.54
Xylene	2.35	4.32
Toluene	2.36	2.54
Carbontetrachloride	2.01	2.34
Methylisobutyl ketone	13.11	1.82
Nitrobenzene	34.81	1.26
<i>n</i> -Butanol	17.64	0.92

butanol. The trend of extraction for organic diluents used follows the order : chloroform > xylene > toluene > carbontetrachloride > methyl isobutyl ketone > nitrobenzene > *n*-butanol.

Effect of extractant concentration on extraction :

The influence of variation of the *N*-acetyl benzamide concentration on the extraction of uranium(VI) ions was examined by changing its concentration. It is clear from the result that with increasing extractant concentration an increase in the extraction of uranium(VI) was observed. A linear increase of distribution coefficient (D_o) was found with increasing extractant concentration. The log-log plot in Fig. 2 gives slope close to 2, indicating the involvement of two molecules of the extractant in the complex formation with uranium(VI) and the composition of the

Fig. 2. Variation of uranium(VI) distribution ratios with *N*-acetyl benzamide extractant in chloroform at fixed pH-value.

extracted species of the type $[\text{UO}_2 \cdot (\text{L})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})]$. Similar conclusion was drawn from pH variation data.

The overall binary extraction is described as,

D_o is the distribution coefficient of uranium(VI) with only *N*-acetyl benzamide in chloroform and defined by,

$$D_o = \frac{[\text{UO}_2 \cdot (\text{L})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})]_{(\text{org})}}{[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]_{(\text{aq})}} \quad (2)$$

Thus equilibrium constant (*k*) for binary extraction is related to the distribution coefficient by,

$$\log k = \log D_o - 2 \log [\text{HL}] - 2 \text{pH} \quad (3)$$

Synergistic extraction of U^{VI} complex in presence of donors :

The effects of various neutral donor concentrations on extraction of U^{VI} with *N*-benzoyl acetamide were examined by keeping the metal ion concentration and equilibrium pH fixed. It was found that under the present experimental conditions, the extent of extraction of uranium(VI) with basic donor were not very appreciable although in presence of such basic donor, the distribution coefficient value of U^{VI} increases with increasing donor concentration, at fixed extractant concentration (Table 2). This is attributed to the formation of a more lipophilic adduct with these donors. In the ternary extraction system, the log [*D_{mix}* - *D'_o*] vs log [HL] plots at fixed concentration of donor and fixed pH of aqueous phase yielded slope of ~2 (Fig. 3), while the log [*D_{mix}* - *D'_o*] vs log [donor] plots at fixed concentration each of three ligands and fixed pH of aqueous phase showed straight line behavior with a slope also ~1 in (Fig. 4), suggesting the composition of the extracted species of the type

Fig. 3. The plot of log [*D_{mix}* - *D'_o*] vs log [Ligand] in synergistic extraction of uranium(VI) with *N*-acetyl benzamide in presence of different donors into chloroform solvent. [Donor] = $0.310 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

[UO₂.(L₂).*(S)*]. In synergistic extraction the increasing values of distribution coefficient is presumably due to the high hydrophobicity of the extracted complexes [UO₂.(L₂).*(S)*] than [UO₂.(L₂).*(H₂O)*]. The overall reaction of the generally accepted synergistic extraction of uranium(VI) is given by eq. (4) where two molecules of

Table 2. Synergistic extraction of U^{VI} with fixed concentration of ligand in presence different concentration of donor

[Ligand] = $1.051 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, *D_o* = 1.091 at pH = 3.0, solvent = CHCl₃

Donor	Conc. of donor (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>D_s</i>	<i>D_{mix}</i>	Δ <i>D</i>	S.C.	log β
Pyridine	0.310×10^{-3}	0.133	1.815	0.591	0.171	3.242
	0.512×10^{-3}	0.185	2.269	0.993	0.249	3.251
	0.724×10^{-3}	0.269	2.278	1.418	0.224	3.254
	0.936×10^{-3}	0.376	3.378	1.911	0.362	3.272
	1.047×10^{-3}	0.421	3.884	2.372	0.409	3.315
TOPO	0.310×10^{-3}	0.251	1.754	0.412	0.117	3.081
	0.512×10^{-3}	0.438	2.194	0.665	0.158	3.074
	0.724×10^{-3}	0.531	2.546	0.924	0.195	3.065
	0.936×10^{-3}	0.634	2.976	1.251	0.236	3.082
	1.047×10^{-3}	0.712	3.275	1.472	0.259	3.121
DMSO	0.310×10^{-3}	0.123	1.455	0.241	0.078	2.854
	0.512×10^{-3}	0.214	1.666	0.351	0.103	2.795
	0.724×10^{-3}	0.341	1.901	0.469	0.124	2.776
	0.936×10^{-3}	0.382	2.177	0.704	0.169	2.832
	1.047×10^{-3}	0.417	2.331	0.823	0.189	2.863

where, S.C. = Synergistic coefficient = $\log D_{\text{mix}} / (D_o + D_s)$ and β (mol⁻¹) = $(D_{\text{mix}} - D'_o) / D_o [S]$, apparent formation constant *S* = Donor.

Fig. 4. The plot of $\log [D_{\text{mix}} - D'_o]$ vs $\log [\text{Donor}]$ in synergistic extraction of uranium(VI) with $1.051 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ *N*-acetyl benzamide in presence of different donor.

extractant and one molecule donor (S) are present in the extracted adduct.

Hence, ternary adduct formation may be described as,

Obviously, equilibrium constant (*K*) is shown by

$$K = \frac{[\text{UO}_2 \cdot (\text{L})_2 \cdot (\text{S})]_{(\text{org})} [\text{H}^+]^2_{(\text{aq})}}{[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]_{(\text{aq})} [\text{S}]_{(\text{org})}} \quad (5)$$

But, distribution coefficient (D_{mix}) for mixed extraction is,

$$D_{\text{mix}} = \frac{[\text{UO}_2 \cdot (\text{L})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})]_{(\text{aq})} + [\text{UO}_2 \cdot (\text{L})_2 \cdot (\text{S})]_{(\text{org})} + [\text{UO}_2 \cdot (\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot (\text{S})]_{(\text{org})}}{[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]_{(\text{aq})}} \quad (6)$$

D_s is the distribution coefficient of the uranium(VI) with neutral donor alone in toluene solvent.

$$D_s = \frac{[\text{UO}_2 \cdot (\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot (\text{S})]_{(\text{org})}}{[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]_{(\text{aq})}} \quad (7)$$

Combining eqs. (2), (5), (6) and eq. (7), we get

$$K = \frac{[D_{\text{mix}} - D'_o][\text{H}^+]^2_{(\text{aq})}}{[\text{HL}]^2_{(\text{org})} [\text{S}]_{(\text{org})}} \quad (8)$$

Taking logarithm and rearranging,

$$\log K = \log (D_{\text{mix}} - D'_o) - 2 \log [\text{HL}]_{(\text{org})} - \log [\text{S}]_{(\text{org})} - 2 \text{pH} \quad (9)$$

where, $D'_o = D_o + D_s$

It is clear from eq. (9) that the plot of $\log (D_{\text{mix}} - D'_o)$ vs $\log [\text{S}]_{(\text{org})}$ at fixed pH and extractant concentration, the slope value will provide the number of donor molecules associated in the adduct. Similarly, from the plot of $\log (D_{\text{mix}} - D'_o)$ vs $\log [\text{HL}]_{(\text{org})}$ at fixed pH and donor concentration, the slope value obtained provides the number of extractant molecules associated in adduct.

The adduct formation reaction in the organic phase may be represented as

where, $K_s = K/k$

Degree of synergism and equilibrium constant in extraction :

The extraction of U^{VI} with neutral donor (D_s) as mentioned before was relatively small under the present experimental conditions. However, with the mixtures of *N*-acetyl benzamide and neutral donor, a considerable synergistic enhancement in the extraction of U^{VI} has been observed. The degree of synergism can be quantified by synergistic coefficient (S.C.). It is used to describe the enhancement in the equilibrium distribution ratio when two or more extractants are used as a mixture for extraction.

$$\text{S.C.} = \log [D_{\text{mix}} / (D'_o + D_s)] \quad (11)$$

where D_m and D_o denote the distribution ratios of a metal ion with mixture of ligand and donor and pure ligand, respectively, in ternary system.

The apparent stability constant (β) is given by :

$$\beta = (D_{\text{mix}} - D'_o) / D_o [\text{donor}] \quad (12)$$

Synergism was observed at all the compositions studied. Keeping the concentration of extractant constant it was observed that the synergistic coefficient increased with an increase in the concentration of the synergist, donor (Table 2) at fixed pH of the aqueous phase. Similarly, keeping donor concentration constant, the synergistic coefficient increased with an increase in the extractant concentration in the organic phase at a given pH (Table 3).

Table 3. Synergistic extraction of U^{VI} by the mixture of *N*-acetyl benzamide and donor

[Pyridine] = 0.31 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [TOPO] = 0.31 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, DMSO = 0.31 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, pH = 3.0, solvent = CHCl₃

Donor	Conc. extractant (mol dm ⁻³)	D _o	D _{mix}	ΔD	S.C	log β
Pyridine	0.702 × 10 ⁻²	0.441	0.749	0.175	0.115	3.107
	1.051 × 10 ⁻²	1.091	1.815	0.591	0.171	3.171
	1.404 × 10 ⁻²	2.342	3.867	1.385	0.194	3.276
	2.106 × 10 ⁻²	5.541	9.032	3.431	0.205	3.301
TOPO	0.702 × 10 ⁻²	0.441	0.815	0.123	0.071	2.953
	1.051 × 10 ⁻²	1.091	1.754	0.412	0.116	3.085
	1.404 × 10 ⁻²	2.342	3.409	0.934	0.139	3.109
	2.106 × 10 ⁻²	5.541	7.965	2.291	0.148	2.972
DMSO	0.702 × 10 ⁻²	0.441	0.649	0.085	0.061	2.791
	1.051 × 10 ⁻²	1.091	1.462	0.248	0.081	2.865
	1.404 × 10 ⁻²	2.342	3.023	0.557	0.088	2.884
	2.106 × 10 ⁻²	5.541	6.743	1.079	0.075	2.798

Again the trend in S.C. shown in Table 2 and Table 3 for basic donors taken up here follow the order : pyridine > TOPO > DMSO. This trend can be correlated with the relative basic natures of the donors. The donation of electron pair by nitrogen in pyridine is stronger due to its low electronegativity compared to that in TOPO in which the oxygen atom is more electronegative. Among the TOPO and DMSO, TOPO extracts better due its higher basicity. Somewhat similar trend was seen in the synergistic extraction of other transition metals and actinides¹³⁻¹⁵. From eqs. (3) and (8) it is possible to evaluate the equilibrium constants for the extraction with pure extractant and in case of mixed extractions after substituting other experimental parameters, as needed by these equations. The values of equilibrium constants of such binary and ternary extraction systems are presented in Table 4. The ternary equilibrium constant value is again highest for pyridine in compare to TOPO or DMSO.

Table 4. Values of the binary and ternary equilibrium extraction constants and synergic adduct formation constants for the extraction of U^{VI} with *N*-acetyl benzamide and mixture of donor in chloroform

Binary system		Ternary system		
System	log <i>k</i>	System	log <i>K</i>	log <i>K_s</i>
Ligand-U ^{VI}	-2.02	Ligand-U ^{VI} -pyridine	1.25	3.27
		Ligand-U ^{VI} -TOPO	1.08	3.10
		Ligand-U ^{VI} -DMSO	0.84	2.86

Extraction mechanism and thermodynamic parameters :

The equilibrium extraction constants log *k* and log *K* for the studied complexes were obtained from the equilibrium metal concentration in the organic and aqueous phase using eqs. (3) and (8). From the values of equilibrium extraction constant at the temperature range investigated, enthalpy changes were calculated using the Vant's Hoff equation^{16,17}.

$$\log K = - \frac{\Delta H^0}{2.303RT} + \frac{\Delta S^0}{2.303R} \quad (13)$$

The plot of log *K* against 1/*T* (Fig. 5) is a straight line where the slope gives the enthalpy of reaction (Δ*H*⁰) and intercept corresponds to entropy (Δ*S*⁰) value and these data were used to obtain the corresponding free energy changes. The results are summarized in Table 5. As seen from the table, the extraction with only ligand, expressed by eq. (3), proceeds non-spontaneously in the forward direction, endothermally with entropy loss. On the other hand, synergistic adduct formation reaction eq. (4) proceeds spontaneously with a considerably higher log *K*, exothermally with low value of entropy gain or loss. The equilibrium constant of the synergistic reaction is relatively high. It was reported¹⁸ that U^{VI} is associated with water molecules in inner sphere in case of extraction by β-diketone. In adduct formation reaction, this coordinated water molecule was released due to the addition of the basic donor. The donor forms stronger adduct bonds re-

Fig. 5. Effect of temperature on the equilibrium extraction constant of uranium(VI) at fixed concentration of *N*-acetyl benzamide in absence and presence of donor into chloroform solvent. The straight line, A : absence of donor, B : presence of pyridine, C : presence of TOPO, D : presence of DMSO.

Table 5. Thermodynamic parameters for extraction of U^{VI} for binary and ternary extraction systems

System	ΔH^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^0 (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹) at 27 °C
Ligand	+8.148	-11.84	+11.701
Ligand-pyridine	-6.804	+2.896	-7.644
Ligand-TOPO	-16.422	-32.88	-6.594
Ligand-DMSO	-18.982	-47.204	-4.746

sulting negative enthalpy change. Hence, both the enthalpy and entropy changes favor the reaction, resulting in relatively large values of $\log K$. Adduct formation reaction in the organic phase for extracted chelates with both DMSO and TOPO are mainly enthalpy stabilized with loss in entropy contribution. It may so happen that there two donors interact through outer sphere complexation mechanism in which donors are accommodated in expanded coordination shell of metal. This results decrease in number of molecules after extraction leading to loss in entropy. However, with pyridine as a donor, both entropy and enthalpy contribute to the stability. In this case, the enthalpy is lower than other two donor systems, which can be explained on the basis of the stronger interaction between pyridine molecule and the metal chelate,

as compared to, other donors. Hence the number of water molecules liberated from metal chelate in presence of pyridine is more and gain in entropy is achieved. Therefore synergistic effect of basic donor is explained by the replacement of the coordinated water molecule from inner coordination sphere of the metal in case of pyridine donor whereas outersphere complexation takes place for TOPO and DMSO.

Infra-red spectroscopy :

The infra-red spectrum of the extracted compound was recorded after evaporating the solvent. From spectral data, it was observed that the characteristic bands for free ligand shift to lower frequencies. The $\nu_{C=N}$ stretching frequency has shifted from free extractant at 1571 cm⁻¹ to lower frequency at 1555 cm⁻¹ other $\nu_{C=O}$ band was shifted from free extractant at 1186 cm⁻¹ to lower frequency at 1171 cm⁻¹. It is noteworthy that the peak at 1615 cm⁻¹ attributed to $\nu_{C=O}$ vibration originating from ketonic form has disappeared, indicating that the extractant remains in enol form in the extracted complexes. This implies that the loss of the acidic proton from enol hydroxyl moieties and bonding of both enol hydroxyl oxygen and enol carbonyl oxygen to the metal ions take place in extracted complex. So the enhanced conjugation from keto-enol tautomer to enol-form hexahydric chelate ring gives a natural interpretation of the lower frequency shifts seen experimentally in the extracted complexes. This shows that the chelating ligand extracted the uranium(VI) metal into organic phase as bidentate one. Similarly the $\nu_{P=O}$ band has been shifted from 1144 cm⁻¹ in free phosphine oxide donor to 1121 cm⁻¹ which characterize the P=O-U bond in adduct complex. More over ν_{U-N} and ν_{U-O} bands were observed at 754 cm⁻¹ and 732 cm⁻¹ respectively¹⁹. This clearly supports the formation of the adduct complex [UO₂.(L)₂.(S)] in the organic phase.

Experimental

Reagents and instrument :

The chelating extractant *N*-acetyl benzamide was synthesised by the reaction of acetamide and benzoyl-chloride, derived from benzoic acid, which were obtained from Aldrich, USA. The donor reagents used in this work e.g. trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO), dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO), pyridine, were also collected from Aldrich,

USA. The solvents were purified by standard procedures. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. A stock solution of uranium was prepared by dissolving A.R. $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Aldrich) in deionised water and a working stock was prepared by appropriate dilution. Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu UV-Vis-6 spectrophotometer. Microanalysis of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content of the synthetic ligand were achieved in a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS-O elemental analyzer. Infrared spectra of ligands and adduct complexes were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer FTIR Model RX1 spectrometer. A Systronics model 335 digital pH-meter equipped with a single electrode was used for pH measurement.

Extraction procedure :

In the general extraction procedure, 5 ml aqueous solution containing 100 μg of U^{VI} solution was adjusted to a pH 3.00 and extracted with equal volume of chloroform solution of different concentrations of chelating ligand for a period of 30 min in a mechanical shaker. Ionic strength of the solution was kept fixed by using of 0.5 mol dm^{-3} KNO_3 reagent. For synergistic study organic phase was mixed with appropriate donor reagent of desired concentration. Concentration of uranium nitrate in aqueous solution was analysed by spectrophotometric technique using 8-hydroxyquinoline²⁰. The distribution coef-

(2.00 g) was refluxed for 2 h with successive addition of thionyl chloride. The excess of chlorinating agent was removed by slow evaporation. In a beaker, a saturated solution of acetamide (1.04 g) in toluene solvent, was prepared. The solvent was purified by drying over calcium oxide followed by distillation before use. This acetamide solution was then condensed with benzoyl chloride for 1 h over a boiling water bath. The light brown color precipitate so appeared was separated by filtration process, recrystallized from chloroform solvent and dried. The dried compound melts at $(98 \pm 2^\circ)$. The proposed formula of the extractant (Scheme 1) is in good agreement with the stoichiometries obtained from their CHN elemental analysis data as well as IR and ^1H NMR data. From CHN analysis, Found : C, 69.26; H, 4.98; N, 8.95. Calcd. : C, 69.67; H, 5.8; N, 9.03. In the IR spectrum of the ligand absence of band at 3760 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} (present in original acid) and presence of sharp peaks at 1615 cm^{-1} and 1587 cm^{-1} indicate that keto-enol tautomerism is present in the synthesised extractant²¹. Other vibration bands are at 1571 cm^{-1} and at 1186 cm^{-1} which are attributed to enol form $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ ²² respectively. These data support that only hydroxyl group of acid takes part in condensation reaction. ^1H NMR data also agrees well, δ , at 7.8 ppm (5H, aromatic), methyl proton occur at 2.4 ppm δ (3H, s, methyl group), amide proton -HN- arise at 9.1 ppm δ (1H, s, proton)²³.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of chelating extractant *N*-acetyl benzamide.

ficient of metal ion was calculated from the U^{VI} concentrations in the aqueous phase before and after attaining equilibrium from the following equation :

$$D = C_{\text{M}}(\text{org})/C_{\text{M}}(\text{aq}) = (C_{\text{M}0} - C_{\text{M}})/C_{\text{M}}$$

where $C_{\text{M}0}$ and C_{M} denote analytical U^{VI} concentrations in the aqueous phase before and after attaining partition equilibrium, respectively.

Synthesis and characterisation of the chelating agent :

The chelating ligand was synthesized by the general condensation reaction between benzoyl chloride and acetamide (1 : 1). The starting material, A.R. benzoic acid

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